

PEDAGOGICAL METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS-TRANSLATORS' PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES

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METODOLOGIA DEZVOLTĂRII COMPETENȚELOR PROFESIONALE ALE STUDENȚILOR-TRADUCTORI

Rezumat. *Articolul abordează o problemă semnificativă pentru calitatea în educație la nivel universitar – dezvoltarea competențelor profesionale ale studenților-traducători – a competențelor de traducere. În acest sens se propune analiza evoluției și dezvoltarea semnificației termenului competențe de traducere din perspectiva pregătirii profesionale a studenților-traducători. Sunt menționate și analizate competențele de traducere relevante profesiei de traducător. În acest context este propusă spre analiză tehnologia de formare a competențelor de traducere ale studenților-traducători.*

Cuvinte-cheie: *competențe de traducere, studenți-traducători, competența strategică, competența comunicativă, competența instrumental-profesională, competența socio-culturală, tehnologia de formare a competențelor de traducere, traducerea scrisă specializată.*

Abstract. *The article addresses an issue significant for the quality in the university education – the development of the translation students' professional competences, therefore that of the translation competences (TC). In this regard, the evolution analysis of the term of translation competence is suggested and a new definition of the term of translation competences from the perspective of the students' professional training in the field of translation is generated. In the present article there are mentioned the identified TC relevant to the translation profession. In this context, the pedagogical methodology for developing students' translation competences is presented for analysis.*

Keywords: *translation competences (TC), translation students, strategic competence (SC), communicative competence (CC), instrumental and professional competence (IPC), sociocultural competence (SCC), translation competences development methodology (TCDM), specialized written translation.*

Introduction

The topic of interest of the present article is *translation* as a pedagogical tool in language teaching and learning, but the main concern is translation as a *competence*. In this regard, on the one hand translation is viewed as one of the major and, definitely, important pedagogical tools to be used daily in teaching English as a foreign language (EFL) once the place of translation in EFL education courses is definitely important. On the other hand, translation is studied and viewed as a competence in general education and in professional development (translation competences), i.e. translation competences necessary to be formed in professional education (educating interpre-

ters and translators). The value of the inclusion of the given component in the disciplines and subjects dedicated to EFL teaching presented to effective teaching of English or any other language as a foreign language and obviously in professional instructing of future translators and interpreters.

The main argument to begin with is a discussion of the place of translation within the framework of developments in the communicative approach and as a medium for language instruction in general. This will lead to a discussion of translation as a process that encompasses more than one basic skill in learning foreign languages i.e. *reading, researching and writing*. The purpose of this article is to show that both roles played by

translation (as a pedagogical tool and a competence) are inseparable in language teaching/learning and translators/interpreters' education. The argument will regard the fact that within a discourse framework, *translation both as a language competence and a teaching technique is relevant*, and in fact needed, to the development of EFL prospective teaching and specialists' professional development in this area.

„In any professional environment, performance is judged according to certain clearly defined objectives and needs, which demand a specific type of competence...” [7, p. 27]. In some official documents these competences are represented and mentioned as a set or groups of skills, abilities and attitudes, viewed as performances or competencies, connected with main types of translation activities [2].

Ch. Schaffner and A. Adab track the developments in the study of *translation as a competence that is composed of different skills*. This term is relatively new and not unanimously recognized among translation scholars. Many definitions of translation competence emerged throughout the years, but in the most general terms translation competence represents „... the underlying system of knowledge, abilities and attitudes required to be able to translate” [7, p. 43].

In this regard, the main objectives of the paper include: establishing and identifying theoretical guidelines in linguistics and pedagogical practice related to translation as a teaching strategy, analysis of the development of the TC meaning as a term from the point of view of pre-service translators' professional training, description of methodological approaches to developing TC, describing the strategies of the pedagogical methodology considered to be followed for the purpose of the students' translation competences development and formulation of scientific conclusions and methodological recommendations on the steps and strategies of the students' TC formation.

The scientific originality of this article is supported by the analysis of translation as a process of vocational training, a description of the evolution of the TC (English) concept and definition development of the term „translation competences” in a new sense, the identification of competences relevant to the profession of a translator. As the

scientific issue consists in finding the solution to such an important problem in this area as the determination of theoretical guidelines in translation as a professional educational activity, as well as the delimitation of certain competences related to the profession of a translator that should be developed as a result of the pedagogical methodology for developing students' TC elaboration and implementation.

The practical value of the thesis of the article reflects the development of university didactics through a visual explanation of the most representative methodological approaches to TC development identified in pedagogical literature and the formulation of scientific conclusions and methodological recommendations regarding the formation of TC at the initial stage of training.

Methodology

According to the *Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, Teaching, Assessment* reedited and published in 2018 [1], translation is used within Mediation Activities [1, p. 105], where students have to fulfill translation tasks such as „translate a written text in speech” or „translate a written text in writing” [1, p. 115]. In this regard, translation can be analyzed as a competence (term used in singular) that is an element within a set of communicative language competences, such as linguistic, socio-linguistic, pragmatic.

As a result, from this perspective translation is viewed as a competence in general culture development, which is also a very important issue for further scientific researches, not in our case. In this paper (and our topic of interest) the professional development of translators and interpreters is treated, and in this connection, first of all, the term TC is used in its plural form of the word „competences”, as it is regarded as professional reference which consists of a set of translation competences. It has been concluded, that these are interdependent competences, identified for the purpose of professional development in the field of translation, which is the main point of interest in this article.

Perhaps one of the most pertinent areas of research in translation studies nowadays concerns attempts to conceptualize and further develop

theoretical and practical background for training of translation abilities and skills. In this respect the notion of *translation competences* (TC) plays a prominent role [3, p. 101]. In general terms, TC is perceived as an underlying knowledge or ability needed to carry out a translation task. So, in this regard, professional competences of a translator should be the following translation competences: *strategic competence (SC)*, *communicative competence (CC)*, *instrumental an professional competence (IPC)* and *sociocultural competence (SCC)*.

To clear up on some issues we would like to present some general definitions of each competence under discussion: SC – concerns developing effective strategies for explicit translation, knowing which translation strategy to implement while translating a specific passage and having the right skills as to how to use it; CC – regards knowledge of the orthopedic, lexical and grammatical rules of the languages involved in the translation process, establishing interpersonal communicative relationships to ensure the accurate decoding and encoding of messages, pragmatic approach to the linguistic, grammatical and lexical code of the two languages, SL and TL; PIC – deals with productive use of electronic sources in the field, electronic dictionaries, search systems and programs, application of the language-source structures to demonstrate communicative charisma; SCC concerns communicative adaptation by decoding the meaning of non-verbal communicative conduct in various cultural environments, it is also the common encyclopedia knowledge [5].

Finally, all these competences form the basic professional competences and are called translation competences, which a skillful specialist in this area of activity should have highly developed in order to perform the task of translation accurately and quickly [4].

Another central idea is that an analysis of the tasks facing the learner in developing translation competences deals with developing the four major skills: reading, writing, listening, and speaking, in any foreign language acquisition process. At this point of foreign language acquisition and teaching the most important factor to be taught, from our perspective and in our vision, is acquiring and teaching vocabulary, which is to be emphasized in the process of teaching, so pedagogical

methodology is dedicated to developing professional competences of a translator, these are the translation competences mentioned above. To be more precise, this involves analyzing the learning burden of words and what it means to know a word. These two ideas are interdependent and related to each other.

Results

As the above-mentioned professional competences of a translator are required for professional mastery, the development of these competences should be the main task while designing educational materials in this field of teaching. However, the present university training practice reveals the presence of certain problems that do not allow effective training and control of the degree of training of the most important translation competences of a future translator. One of the most significant is the problem of training and controlling translation competence development. Due to the specificity of the translator's profession, a foreign language serves both as a main purpose and as a learning means, and the formation of translation competences is the most important objective in professional training of a future translator [6, pp. 13-18].

In order to implement the integrated approach in translators' training at the undergraduate level, it is necessary to identify a group of skills, abilities and attitudes that are formed within translation study of the different translation disciplines, but at the same time, they underlie the professionalism of the future translator. The control of such knowledge would allow an objective assessment of the degree of assimilation, not only of the theoretical or practical orientation, but also of the level of professional skills – in this case, the translation competences.

As it has already been mentioned, the professional competences concerned in this study are the translation competences. They are conceived as a set of professional skills, knowledge and include four types of activities in a foreign language (listening, reading, speaking, and writing), as well as personal qualities and abilities that allow a translator to implement communication in foreign languages effectively in various activities of the daily life: practical, scientific and metho-

dological activities, research, organization, management etc.

The pedagogical methodology designed for the purpose of developing students' translation competences is focused on the system of ideas regarding: a) the correlation of the theoretical aspects for developing TC; b) integrated training of students for understanding, application and integration of basic linguistic concepts from the methodological approach focused on communicative methodology of teaching-learning-assessing of translation strategies, which develop motivation for development both in the foreign language (English) and in the mother tongue, and to form a culture of learning; c) correlating the objectives for developing translation competences in a foreign language at the level of the professional training standards (knowledge/application/integration) with the taxonomy of the educational objectives at the level of attitudes/skills/knowledge; d) determining the stages of formation of the translation competences in/from the English language by following the quality indicators of the teaching-learning-assessing of the translation competences; e) reorientation of the teaching-learning-assessing methodology of the English language from the perspective of integrating the teaching technologies and the disciplines dedicated to translation [6].

The pedagogical methodology involves well-defined stages and their detailed description to ensure that the main goal is achieved. It considers pedagogical, educational and learning technologies, including such features of the teaching methodology as structuring, organization of the materials to be learned, this is achieved, especially through the developed educational instruments in which the lexical and grammatical material are selected and structured, according to the study/educational needs.

In some professional textbooks and books, the translation exercises are divided into: pre-translation, translation and post-translation (proof-reading/editing and post-editing). The pre-translation exercises are meant to create conditions for the successful implementation of the translation process itself, to create the necessary communicative attitude, to check whether students have enough knowledge of language and socio-cultural

awareness, and in order to show how good they are in solving typical translation tasks [4].

The translation exercises are meant to form: the ability to work with a dictionary (explanatory, bilingual); terminological dictionaries; ability to identify, analyze and compare the means of compositional and expressive language; ability to match lexical versions in the source language that correspond to the lexical version of the target language; ability to select the words that constitute and determine the paradigmatic and syntagmatic connections of the source word corresponding to a target word.

Both pre-translation and translation exercises can be used for students to handle translation transformations. Translation exercises usually are followed by post-editing or proof-reading tasks and exercises. So, the three main types or categories of exercises are usually used in translation teaching and learning.

At this point we would like to give a short description of the designed pedagogical methodology, which consists of three stages preceded by a preparatory stage that includes the design and elaboration of the necessary teaching materials and curricula development. So, the three stages are:

1. Developing Translation Competences;
2. Practicing Translation Competences;
3. Consolidating Translation Competences.

These stages along with strategies/didactic activities/selected for each step were implemented in students' translation training. Students had to fulfill the tasks compiled and elaborated for the 1st stage of the technology, then, with a higher degree of difficulty, for the second and third stages.

The first stage, Developing Translation Competences, consists of exercises and tasks selected and designed in order to revise general lexical and grammatical rules of both the SL and the TL. This stage is characterized by using pre-translation exercises with some elements of very simple and short translation tasks. This stage also introduces students into main translation methods and strategies, such as translation based on transposition, antonymous translation, omission, etc.

So, basically this stage can be called the pre-translational analysis and pre-interpretation stage of the sentence and/or the fragments of tex-

ts suggested for translation, the whole stage includes the implementation of pre-translation exercises. Performing translation tasks and exercises supposes using the course book designed for the disciplines in translation, compiled from several practical and theoretical translation sources. At this stage there are practiced activities meant to form the strategic, communicative, instrumental and professional and sociocultural competences. The strategies used at this stage are focused on analyzing and assimilating the lexical and grammatical structures. The related exercises would have such types of tasks as filling in with the necessary word, completing, matching, identifying nouns etc., opening the brackets, finding the equivalent in the TL, unjumbling, etc. For example, the following exercise is dedicated to the topic „Medicine and Health Care”:

Match the Romanian names of the parts of the body with their English counterparts.

bile duct	a) intestinul gros
bladder	b) coloana vertebrală
gall bladder	c) laringe
large intestine	d) pelvis
larynx	e) vezica urinară
pancreas	f) canalul fierei
pelvis	g) splină
spine	h) trahee
spleen	i) pancreas
windpipe	j) vezica biliară

The second stage is entitled „Practicing Translation Competences”. Stage 2 of the suggested pedagogical methodology for developing students' translation competences mainly consists of translation activities. This stage is dedicated to practicing translation followed by didactic activities on editing and post-editing. This stage includes teaching-learning-assessing strategies of TC development and translating the texts/passages of the text from SL into TL using linguistic knowledge of both languages.

The second stage of the pedagogical methodology is aimed at practicing translation by reference to texts from special fields, followed by drafting, editing and post-editing steps, tasks and translation exercises. It includes the translation of text abstracts and passages/paragraphs dedicated to

specialized domains, such as politics, medicine, economics, etc. At this stage, there are used strategies that form abilities to carry out transformations and to use appropriate translation strategies deduced from the context of SL to be translated in TL. At this stage the four translation competences under study are formed they are strategic, communicative, instrumental-professional and socio-cultural. One common exercise for this stage will state the following task:

1. Fill the blanks with the words below. You may use each word only once. Translate the text from SL into TL and edit it.

Bacteria	body	break	dangerous	delicate
disease	eyes	germs	line	liquids
membrane	moisture	mouth	nose	parts
Prick	skin	sneeze	stomach	

How the Body Fights Disease

The is often called „the body's first of defence”. It acts as a armour, resisting many germs that might harm them more parts of the Any in the skin, even a pin , provides an opening for germs. Some enter the body through the and and other natural openings. These are as provided warm and in which germs thrive. When the of the nose and throat becomes irritated, we cough or , blowing out the unwanted substances. Other body also provide a defense against Tears, for example, wash from the Tears also contain substances that fight bacteria. Acid in the kills many germs before they can reach other of the body.

According to the needs and peculiarities of Stage 3, which is called „Consolidating TC”, there are used didactic activities on editing, specifying and eliminating errors, writing and post-writing, performing translations of oral/audiovisual materials, orally and by the method of written translation, oriented to professional development, in accordance with the translation algorithm, written translation, editing and post-editing. At this point, the analysis of the translation of the subtitles from different video sequences dedicated to specialized topics are translated with the help of certain software and applications.

This stage is characterized by finding, correcting and removing mistakes/errors through dif-

ferent didactic strategies such as individual, pair and teamwork. Students are given some sentences, statements, paragraphs, texts and speeches translated, for example, with the help of Google Translate and other software that obviously need to be edited. This stage is a creative one and shows how deep a learner's knowledge of the SL and TL is and how well the competences, skills, capacities (at linguistic, sociocultural, psychological, affective levels) are formed.

It shows the levels of the four translation competences as low – medium – high: strategic, communicative, instrumental and professional and sociocultural. As well this stage is characterized by the constant use of simulating activities and creative translation tasks on different specialized topics under study, for example:

Card 1. Topic: HEALTH CARE AND MEDICINE.

Task role-play a situation when:

Roles: a patient (foreigner), a doctor, an interpreter.

Patient Foreigner, you are an Englishman in Moldova: you are abroad on vacation, you have a soar throat, you want to see a doctor, have an appointment with one, you need a translator/interpreter.

Translator/interpreter: you help an Englishman in Moldova see a doctor, main task to interpret the statements;

Doctor (Moldovan): your task is to ask questions and help the patient.

Remember: use the topical vocabulary and essential vocabulary under study. Each participant has to participate with at least 5 statements positive, interrogative, etc.

In our opinion, the combination of the three stages presented shortly in this article in the form of worksheets, exercises, didactic activities, tasks on translation of specialized texts and audiovisual materials (on specialized topics), as well as various editing and post-editing activities, contribute to the integrated formation of the basic elements and values of translation competences identified as being relevant and essential to be formed as students' professional competences.

Translation methods, strategies and technologies used in activities as specialized translation

exercises on different topics, subtitles, at-sight translations, peer translation, creative translation activities, translations recordings and their analysis by colleagues, working with the dictionary, lexical and grammatical exercises, analysis of texts, tasks including predictions and others, have been used to form the values of the identified translation competences necessary to be developed while training future translators.

We consider that the activities and pedagogical methodology proposed as a part of this study develop precision, responsibility, digital skills supposing using different online platforms, the ability to work in disadvantageous or stressful conditions. It is extremely important to use a variety of activities in order to facilitate the process of developing translation competences.

These will be directed towards enriching knowledge about the cultural elements of the languages used. Therefore, a future translator must possess the following qualities: accuracy, responsibility, a tendency towards perfection and quality improvement, the ability to work consistently, advanced digital skills. We believe that achieving these objectives is also possible through our personal input that consists in developing the pedagogical methodology in training future translators.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the four translation competences identified and aimed to being formed as professional competences of a translator are strategic, communicative, instrumental and professional and sociocultural. These competences are aimed at being developed at a very high level. The result is that knowing a foreign language and a mother tongue at a high level is required in order to carry out translation tasks with much accuracy, responsibility as for rendering the message of the SL into TL.

The designed pedagogical methodology consists of three stages, each stage following the previous one, having logical connection and continuing the topic with the emphasis on forming the four TC. As a result, each stage involves a certain type of dominant exercises, which lead to the formation of certain TC.

Thus, in the first stage, the students do lexical and grammatical exercises, which mainly form

communicative and strategic competences. In the second stage, students carry out written translation of specialized texts with many editing and post-editing activities, aimed at developing reading and writing skills, using different professional instruments (electronic dictionaries, etc.), so emphasis on developing such TC as strategic, instrumental and professional and sociocultural.

In the third stage, students perform many simulation tasks, as well as carrying out written translation of the audiovisual sequences, that is to say, the audition of the video fragments in specialized fields. The respective exercises aim at deve-

loping the listening skills in the source language and the written reproduction of the information in the target language. All these stages tend to develop the TC referred to as translator's professional competences in this work.

Finally, since all the exercises used are structured with the purpose to form the above-mentioned TC and aimed at reaching high standards, they are supposed to contribute to achieving good results in instructing translation students. Moreover, translating by its very nature has to unite form with function and this is one important benefit from translating.

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